

Impacts of ADS-B In Approach Applications during Revenue Operations

Measurements and Results from multi-year ADS-B In demonstration

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Abstract— The Federal Aviation Administration’s Automatic Dependent Surveillance – Broadcast (ADS-B) In Retrofit Spacing (AIRS) evaluation demonstrated the operational feasibility and value of ADS-B In capabilities. As part of this project, American Airlines equipped their entire Airbus A321 fleet with avionics necessary to perform multiple applications. The avionics included an ADS-B Guidance Display (AGD) that is used to designate surrounding traffic and obtain information on relevant distance, speed, and altitude. Two of the proposed applications provide benefits on approach. American started using the Cockpit Display of Traffic Information (CDTI) Assisted Visual Separation (CAVS) application in May of 2021 and this application can be used wherever they operate. The CDTI Assisted Separation on Approach (CAS-A) application involves new air traffic controller procedures. The paper presents recent analyses, results, and benefits estimates for both CAVS and CAS-A using 24 months of data. When pilots designate traffic on the AGD, they tend, on average, to achieve more consistent and smaller interarrival distances at the runway threshold. Furthermore, when pilots using an AGD are controlled by TRACON controllers who can recognize the equipped traffic and use a procedure like CAS-A, the result is flight time and distance savings in the terminal area.

Keywords—component; ADS-B In, Cockpit Applications, Visual Separation, Airport Throughput, Interarrival time, Interarrival distance, Airborne Separation

I. INTRODUCTION

The Surveillance and Broadcast Services (SBS) program provides the FAA with upgraded surveillance capabilities and services through currently available satellite-enabled technology. The primary tool for these improvements is Automatic Dependent Surveillance-Broadcast (ADS-B). The SBS program also bundles supporting technologies directed at lowering agency, operator, and the National Airspace System (NAS) user operating costs, while enhancing safety, capacity, productivity, and efficiency.

The primary focus of the SBS program since 2007 has been to deploy ground infrastructure and automation to support air traffic management surveillance using signals transmitted from the aircraft (ADS-B Out). To be an effective surveillance source for separation, all users in a controlled airspace must be equipped. A major factor affecting equipage is an ADS-B Out equipage mandate for all users operating in airspace called out under 14 Code of

Federal Regulations (CFR) 91.225 [1]. This ADS-B Out rule went into effect in January 2020.

The overall strategy of the SBS program has always been to deploy an infrastructure that can be leveraged for future operational improvements. One of the many proposed operational improvements is the use of information received in the cockpit via ADS-B In. ADS-B In applications have been developed for commercial and private users. So far, the most widespread use of ADS-B In has been by the general aviation community that primarily use safety and traffic situational awareness applications [2]. This includes the Flight Information Surveillance-Broadcast (FIS-B) and Traffic Information Surveillance-Broadcast (TIS-B) applications that use the same frequency.

Now that the transition to full ADS-B Out equipage is complete, there is a renewed interest in ADS-B In applications that improve efficiency for larger air transport operators. ADS-B In applications are an avenue for increased throughput being considered by both the FAA [3] and industry. In 2020, the joint FAA/industry Equip 2020 group developed an ADS-B In Strategy Document that included the following reasoning [4]:

“Air transport operators have invested in equipping their fleets with ADS-B Out equipment to meet the ADS-B Mandate in 2020. Operators are now looking forward to the benefits from ADS-B In applications to build on their ADS-B Out investments. ADS-B In applications provide opportunities for significant gains in efficiency, capacity, and safety in the U.S. NAS, especially when integrated with Trajectory-Based Operations (TBO), which promises benefits in high-density operations.”

One of the most promising uses of flight-deck based tools is to increase throughput by increasing the accuracy and precision of airborne spacing. There has been significant prior research concerning the use of flight-deck based tools to either achieve or maintain desired spacing both in Europe and the US [5-17]. These studies have used differing terminology over time: Free Flight, Self Separation, Airborne Separation Assurance System (ASAS), Limited Delegation of Separation, Airborne Spacing and Merging, Flight-deck-based Separation, Cockpit Traffic Display based Separation. The analyses have included concept descriptions and validations, fast-time simulations, human-in-the-loop simulations, and limited operational demonstrations all showing large potential benefits for such

spacing if it can be safely applied and necessary procedures are created. As of 2025, sustained operational benefits of such cockpit-based separation applications during revenue operations have not successfully come to fruition because of limited equipage and lack of associated ANSP procedures.

The FAA’s ADS-B In Retrofit Spacing (AIRS) evaluation was a demonstration of the operational feasibility and value of ADS-B In capabilities using a retrofit avionics solution. As part of this project, American Airlines equipped their entire Airbus A321 fleet (298 aircraft) with avionics necessary to perform multiple applications. The avionics included an ADS-B Guidance Display (AGD) that can be used to designate surrounding traffic and obtain information on relevant distance, speed, and altitude information. Figure 1 shows the location of the AGD in the cockpit and other related displays. These include the Navigation Display and the Multi-function Control Display Unit (MCDU). Figure 2 presents a close-up of the AGD and highlights some of the available information.

FIGURE 1. ACSS SAFEROUTE+ AVIONICS COMPONENTS, PHOTO COURTESY OF ACSS, LLC.

II. ADS-B IN APPLICATIONS: CAVS AND CAS-A

There are two applications that both use the AGD during approach. Both applications refer to the use of the AGD as a Cockpit Display of Traffic Information (CDTI):

1. CDTI Assisted Visual Separation (CAVS),
2. CDTI Assisted Separation on Approach (CAS-A).

The CAVS application supports the flight crew when performing visual separation on approach to the same runway in Visual Meteorological Conditions (VMC). ATC issues a visual approach clearance and advises the flight crew to maintain visual separation from traffic. The flight crew must first visually acquire the traffic out the window (OTW) and then correlate that sighting with the CAVS can be conducted in conjunction with existing visual arrival operations and does not require any additional infrastructure or modification to ATC procedures. The use of CAVS by the flight crew is unknown to ATC and does not change controller-pilot separation responsibilities.

FIGURE 2. EXAMPLE OF CDTI WITH CAVS INFORMATION, PHOTO COURTESY OF ACSS, LLC.

Once the traffic is designated in the CAVS equipment, the distance to traffic and the ground speed differential is displayed in the pilot’s forward field of view. Figure 2 includes an operational example of such a display. In addition, the flight crew gets a caution alert if the aircraft is 1.4 nautical miles (NM) or closer to another aircraft. The additional information aids the flight crew in assessing the acceptability of the distance between ownship and the designated aircraft.

The CAVS application allows the flight crew to lose OTW visual contact with traffic-to-follow (after being designated) and still maintain visual separation. The details are provided in Appendix B of FAA Advisory Circular 90-114B, Change 1 [18]. This allows pilot-applied visual separation on approach to continue in conditions where it may be difficult or impossible to maintain OTW visual contact throughout the approach. Examples include traffic being obscured by haze, bright sunlight, or city lights at night, or traffic blending with the ground.

CAVS is part of the AIRS operational evaluation and was approved by the FAA for NAS-wide use by American Airlines in May 2021.

CAVS has the potential to provide benefits for all visual operations on approach, not just those where traffic is obscured from view. CAVS is expected to improve traffic awareness and the pilot’s visual separation task, as well as help the pilot maintain visual separation requirements during day and night VMC.

Like CAVS, the objective of the CAS-A application is to maintain pilot-applied visual-like separation safely and more efficiently from a lead aircraft via the CDTI during approach procedures [19]. It is expected to recapture some of the runway capacity lost under visual separation operations during weather conditions when identification of the lead aircraft OTW may be challenging or impossible.

CAS-A builds on the existing CAVS operation. The same flight deck tools are used for both CAS-A and CAVS. The CAS-A operation is initiated by the controller, who provides an approach clearance and a CAS-A instruction that includes the aircraft callsign for the traffic-to-follow. The flight crew identifies the lead aircraft on the CDTI based on the aircraft callsign provided by the controller, and visual acquisition out-the-window is not required. After traffic identification by the flight crew and designation in the avionics, the flight crew uses the designated aircraft's information on the CDTI to conduct pilot-applied separation operations.

CAS-A can only be used when both aircraft are approaching the same runway. CAS-A does not modify VMC or Instrument Meteorological Conditions (IMC) minima. CAS-A can be conducted when the destination airport has a reported ceiling of 1,000 feet or greater and visibility of three statute miles or greater. The aircraft conducting a CAS-A operation may enter IMC conditions when on an instrument approach but must remain clear of clouds when on a visual approach. Figure 3 shows a graphical depiction of a CAS-A operation [19].

FIGURE 3. CAS-A OPERATION

CAS-A does not change any requirements for instrument or visual approach procedures. It allows the flight crew to use the CDTI alone to maintain separation from the designated aircraft when OTW visual contact is not possible or is lost. CAS-A also does not change any controller or pilot procedures related to wake vortex limitations.

CAS-A operations were exclusively used by controllers at D10 for DFW arrivals. Their use began in March 2023 and continued through the end of the demonstration in February 2025.

III. DATA SOURCES

Multiple data sources were used for the AIRS project analyses. The following sections describe the data sources and the reasons each was used.

A. IOAA Trajectory Data

The Instrument Flight Procedures (IFP), Operations, and Airspace Analytics (IOAA) Tool provides analysis capabilities to study flight operational metrics and implementation/use of Instrument Flight Procedures (IFP) [20]. It enables analysis of fused operational usage metrics (e.g., arrival procedure usage), aircraft performance metrics (e.g., climb gradient distributions, final approach

deviations), and weather conditions at various points of interest in the NAS. Users can dynamically filter parameters within the tool to quickly correlate between metrics and identify flights of interest. The fused surveillance data used to derive operational usage, safety, and aircraft performance metrics is available for both display and download.

IOAA Threaded Track data combines FAA radar, Airport Surface Detection Equipment Model X (ASDE-X), and ADS-B data to create a fused end-to-end trajectory for each flight. IOAA trajectory data undergoes multiple quality checks before release. For the AIRS project, this trajectory data was downloaded to examine individual flight profiles for all arrivals into six major American Airline hub airports: Charlotte International Airport (CLT), Dallas-Fort Worth International Airport (DFW), Los Angeles International Airport (LAX), Miami International Airport (MIA), Philadelphia International Airport (PHL), and Phoenix International Airport (PHX).

B. CountOps

CountOps is an FAA automated system that utilizes data from the National Offload Program (NOP) and Standard Terminal Automation Replacement System (STARS) to provide hourly counts of air traffic activity at TRACONs, towers, and airports. It includes counts for more than 2,000 towers and airports [21]. CountOps also contains information on individual arrival and departure operations.

For the AIRS program, CountOps is particularly useful because it contains scratchpad information for individual flights. At Dallas TRACON (D10) the scratchpad for DFW arrivals includes either the code "IC" or "VC" to indicate a CAS-A operation. The data collection team uses this information to count CAS-A operations and correlate this data to flights from the IOAA trajectory data.

C. ACSS SafeRoute+ Data

SafeRoute data refers to parameters recorded by the ACSS Traffic Alert Collision and Avoidance System (TCAS) surveillance processor. This includes parameters related to surrounding ADS-B traffic, the host aircraft, and the SafeRoute+ applications. SafeRoute+ data is used to identify flights where aircraft designation was used and provide useful metrics.

ACSS developed a process to obtain SafeRoute+ data from the aircraft using Compact Flash (CF) cards placed in TCAS units (see Figure 4). American Airlines maintenance retrieves the CF cards from the TCAS units periodically, typically twice a month.

FIGURE 4. PROCESS TO OBTAIN SAFEROUTE+ DATA FROM THE AIRCRAFT

Upon receiving the CF cards or CF card data, ACSS used the following process:

1. Removed the raw data files for temporary storage and processing.
2. Identified flights with ADS-B In equipment, those using traffic designation
3. Calculated SafeRoute+ data parameters (see Table 1).
4. Provided the SafeRoute+ data to the FAA (semi-monthly).
5. Erased the data on the CF card (header information is kept for future filtering).
6. Mailed the blank CF cards back to American Airlines maintenance (ACSS maintained configuration management of the CF Cards).

Each set of data can contain information from previous months. For this reason, there was a lag in the availability of complete monthly data sets for all flights. The lag depended on when the data can be physically downloaded from each aircraft. Typically, the lag was as long as three months in duration.

TABLE I. ACSS PROVIDED DATA PER DESIGNATED TRAFFIC OPERATION

ACSS Data Element	Format
Own Tail Number	Tail Number
Own Flight ID	Three-letter call sign and number
Own Pressure Altitude	Pressure altitude of ownship at beginning of designation (feet above mean sea level [ft msl])
Own Ground Speed	Ground speed at beginning of designation (knots)
Designated Traffic Flight ID	Three-letter callsign and number
Designation Date Start	Time UTC (HH:MM:SS)
Designation Time Start	Time UTC (HH:MM:SS)
Designation Time End	Time UTC (HH:MM:SS)
Traffic Pressure Altitude	Pressure altitude of traffic at beginning of designation (ft msl)
Horizontal Range	Horizontal range from designated aircraft at beginning of designation (NM)

D. ASPM

Aviation System Performance Metrics (ASPM) is an FAA-maintained database that contains a variety of flight and airport information [22]. ASPM data falls into two categories: flight data containing information on individual flight performance and airport data containing information on airport efficiency. Data comes from ARINC's Out-Of-On-In (OOOI), Traffic Flow Management System (TFMS), US Department of Transportation's Airline Service Quality Performance (ASQP) survey, weather data, airport arrival and departure rates (in 15-minute intervals), airport runway configurations, delays, cancellations, and arrival/departure

rates. For this effort, data from ASPM was correlated with the ACSS data to limit analysis to aircraft callsigns arriving at airports of interest, and to define different periods of meteorological conditions at the relevant airports.

IV. METRICS AND ANALYSIS APPROACH

A. Number of relevant operations

As described in the previous section, ACSS provides a row of data every time a relevant aircraft designates traffic on the AGD. Data from ASPM is used to identify the registration number of all American A321 aircraft arriving at each destination airport. An inventory of equipped aircraft was used to track equipped flights arriving at each airport. The data collection team correlated the aircraft callsign, date, and time from the ACSS data with IOAA trajectory data to determine flight destination, destination airport runway, and distance from destination airport. The data were aggregated by airport and analyses performed at six American Airlines hubs.

The following CAVS/Traffic Designation count metrics were examined per airport:

- Monthly number of equipped arrivals.
- Monthly number and percent of equipped arrivals using traffic designation between 25 NM and the airport. The reasoning behind this metric is to determine which arrivals are using traffic designation during the approach.

The CAS-A operation is exclusively used by D10 for DFW arrivals. CountOps data (see Section III.B) includes data entered into the data block scratchpad by controllers. D10 controllers enter a specified code (either "VC" or "IC") in the scratchpad to indicate a CAS-A operation.

The following CAS-A count metrics were examined at DFW:

- Monthly number of equipped arrivals
- Monthly number and percent of equipped arrivals using CAS-A.

B. Interarrival Time and Interarrival Distance

CAVS and CAS-A can assist the pilot in more precisely acquiring and maintaining visual separation. The objective of these procedures is to maintain visual-like separation to the lead aircraft safely and more efficiently via the CDTI during approach.

On an individual aircraft basis, the most obvious metrics to examine the effectiveness of CAVS and CAS-A are measures of interarrival time and distance at the runway threshold. The primary metrics used for the analyses were:

- Interarrival Time (IAT) –the time between ownship threshold time and previous arrival threshold time on same runway.
- Interarrival Distance (IAD) –the distance between ownship and the previous arrival when the lead aircraft crosses threshold.

The data was gathered per arrival for all flights into each runway for American Airlines hub airports. The analysis examined the characteristics of IAT and IAD data using the following factors to group results:

- Use of CAVS/Traffic Designation capability.
- Use of CAS-A (D10 for DFW arrivals only).
- Aircraft type.
- Carrier name.
- Weather conditions.
- Demand at the airport in terms of number of arrivals in front of ownship during the past 15 minutes.
- Weight class of heavy for lead aircraft.

The metrics were grouped into sets and analyzed, including direct examination of the distributions and descriptive statistics (average, median, mode, standard deviation), statistical tests on the difference of the averages and standard deviations, average value vs. demand, and multiple linear regression using ordinary least squares regression.

For the distribution, statistical testing, and trend analysis the following restrictions were applied to compare relevant sets:

- Limited analysis to A321 and A321 neo (A21N) aircraft.
- Removed arrivals with IATs > 220 sec or < 40 sec.
- Removed arrivals behind a heavy (wake category) aircraft.
- Removed arrivals during IMC (<1000 feet ceiling or <3 miles visibility).

For the analyses, the data was filtered as outlined above and then the averages, distributions, and trends were examined comparing American Airlines A321 aircraft which used Traffic Designation within 25 NM of the airport (or were assigned a CAS-A procedure) to those which did not.

Regression analyses were also used to examine simultaneous impacts. Regression results include the coefficients of each independent variable, the significance of the coefficient (in terms of the P-value) and the overall goodness of fit of the model (adjusted R-Square).

C. Flight time/Path length in Terminal Area

One possible impact of decreasing IAT and IAD is a reduction in flight time or path length for the equipped aircraft and nearby aircraft. The analysis focused on flight time and path length inside a ring with a radius of 25 NM from the center of the airport. Figure 5 shows such a ring around DFW, as well as sample flight paths.

The primary metrics used were:

- Flight time – the time flown between entering a 25 NM radius ring centered on the airport and the runway threshold.
- Flight distance – the distance flown between a 25 NM radius ring centered on the airport and the runway threshold.

FIGURE 5. SAMPLE DFW ARRIVAL FLIGHT PATHS WITH A 25 NM RADIUS CIRCLE AROUND AIRPORT

Most airports have established weather minima below which visual separation cannot be conducted, in part due to the difficulty in visually acquiring traffic in such conditions. Even in visual conditions, acquiring and maintaining visual separation can be difficult. This is especially true at night, during sunrise or sunset, or when haze is present. By using traffic designation, the CAVS and CAS-A procedures can assist the pilot in more precisely acquiring and maintaining visual separation in less-than-optimal weather conditions.

While weather is not an operational metric, it is an important factor in the analyses, and the selection of different weather categories impacts the results. The analyses categorize weather by ceiling and visibility at the airport (as opposed to on arrival or during approach), primarily because this is the data that is available. The following definitions were used:

- Instrument Meteorological Conditions (IMC) uses basic minimums (<1000 ft ceiling or < 3 miles visibility).
- Marginal Meteorological Conditions 1 (MMC1) is based on a Visual Approach Threshold value listed in ASPM for DFW (<3500 ft ceiling or < 5 miles visibility).
- Marginal Meteorological Conditions 2 (MMC2) is based on information gathered from the facility personnel (<6000 ft ceiling or <= 8 miles visibility).

While IMC is a common definition in air traffic management, MMC1 and MMC2 were defined by the AIRS data team for this study to better examine the impact of weather conditions described by controllers using CAS-A. Figure 6 presents a diagram of the ceiling and visibility regimes used in the DFW analyses.

Another significant factor in flight distance/time is the direction of the flow as compared to where an aircraft enters the terminal area. A “Downwind” refers to an aircraft that must fly parallel to the landing runway, but in

FIGURE 6. WEATHER REGIMES USED IN DFW ANALYSES

the opposite direction of the intended landing before making a turn and approaching the runway (there is a clear example of this type of pattern in Figure 5). Being on a downwind can significantly add to the flight time and distance in the terminal area.

Multiple linear regression was used to control for various factors that affect flight time and distance in the terminal area. The only data removed from the analysis were flights during IMC. The dependent variables were gathered for all aircraft and the regressions included dependent demand variables to test the impact of different types of aircraft or operations landing in front of each flight.

Different interaction terms were also examined (e.g., CAS-A and Downwind or Number of CAS-A arrivals in 15 minutes and MMC2) to test impacts that may only occur in certain situations. Correlation matrices were examined to make sure the independent variables were not correlated above a certain amount (leading to misleading results). Different regression specifications were used for different analyses of the data. The results section lists the variables used in each analysis. Regression results included the coefficients of each independent variable, the significance of the coefficient (expressed as the P-value), and the overall goodness of fit of the model (adjusted R-squared).

V. RESULTS

A. Traffic Designation, CAVS, and CAS-A use

The ACSS avionics package including the AGD allows traffic designation any time during a flight and can be used multiple times per flight. Consequently, pilots have been using traffic designation to gain additional traffic situational awareness in all phases of flight. Figure 7 presents the number of traffic designations grouped by arrival airport for the period September 2020 through September 2024 (49 months). This analysis used the ACSS traffic designation data (that includes aircraft callsign) and ASPM to determine arrival airport based on callsign and time of designation. “Other” in Figure 7 refers to flights en route to all airports not listed in the table.

All subsequent analysis in this report is focused on operations at DFW. For additional information and analyses and results at other American Airlines hubs see [24].

FIGURE 7. TRAFFIC DESIGNATION FOR AMERICAN A321S

CAVS and CAS-A operations are focused on traffic designation during approach. Table II presents the monthly total arrivals, AAL A321 arrivals, the arrivals using traffic designation within a 25 NM circle around DFW, and the flights that received a CAS-A procedure during the period March 2023 through February 2025 (24 months). Note that American Airlines pilots have been using traffic designation extensively since May 2021; however, this analysis is focused on the period when both CAVS and CAS-A were available at DFW. For more details on the use of traffic designation prior to March 2023 see [24].

TABLE II. TRAFFIC DESIGNATION AND CAS-A OPERATIONS AT DFW (MAR 2023-FEB 2025)

Month	Total arrivals	AAL A321 and A21N arrivals	Designating Traffic within 25 NM of Runway	CAS-A arrivals
3/2023	28,364	5,521	1,354	282
4/2023	27,549	5,326	1,146	100
5/2023	29,202	5,707	1,453	276
6/2023	30,502	5,871	1,546	227
7/2023	31,564	6,113	1,226	177
8/2023	31,827	6,086	1,498	332
9/2023	28,890	5,501	1,542	269
10/2023	30,215	5,847	1,744	116
11/2023	28,602	5,396	1,471	107
12/2023	29,040	5,546	1,252	70
1/2024	27,871	4,737	1,524	52
2/2024	27,333	5,113	1,558	107
3/2024	30,498	5,533	1,505	136
4/2024	29,325	5,168	1,126	110
5/2024	30,573	5,318	1,348	74
6/2024	32,653	5,952	1,541	107
7/2024	34,217	6,192	1,637	140
8/2024	33,195	5,719	1,478	85
9/2024	30,704	5,079	1,399	84
10/2024	33,058	5,778	1,621	52
11/2024	29,852	5,251	1,464	22
12/2024	31,214	5,564	1,583	32
1/2025	28,568	5,121	1,479	20
2/2025	27,164	4,861	662*	34

*The February Designating data in Table II is likely low because of lag in the aircraft data.

Table II displays a decrease in CAS-A use over time. There were a few reasons for this decrease:

- There was a change in local management and emphasis on the evaluation.
- With no automation to indicate CAS-A capable aircraft, controllers had to be continually reminded of CAS-A.
- A change in procedures mandating the use of specific turns, altitudes, and speeds in some cases reduced use.

The analysis used the ACSS traffic designation data and IOAA trajectory data to determine the distance from the arrival airport. CAS-A operations are identified directly using CountOps scratchpad data to identify CAS-A operations.

B. Interarrival Time and Interarrival Distance

Interarrival Time (IAT) and Interarrival Distance (IAD) were examined in multiple ways. The analyses were limited to American Airlines A321 and A21N arrivals during the period March 2023 to February 2025 (24 months). The analysis only considered IATs between 40 and 220 seconds apart to focus on period of high demand, removed arrivals behind a heavy (wake category) aircraft, and arrivals during IMC.

Table III presents descriptive statistics (average, median, standard deviation, and number of observations) of the IAT and IAD at DFW for three cases: arrivals not using traffic designation on approach (Not Designating), arrivals using traffic designation within 25 NM of the airport (Designating), and arrivals receiving a CAS-A approach.

TABLE III. IAT AND IAD METRICS AT DFW

Apt	A321 and A21N Metrics	Not Designating	Designating	CAS-A
IAT	Average IAT (sec)	112	97	97
	Median IAT (sec)	101	91	93
	Standard Deviation	37	26	25
	Observations	69,870	29,532	2,618
IAD	Average IAD (NM)	4.6	3.9	3.9
	Median IAD (NM)	4.0	3.6	3.7
	Standard Deviation	1.7	1.1	1.1
	Observations	69,870	29,532	2,618

Visualizations of the spacing distributions were also prepared. Figures 8 and 9 present the IAT and IAD distributions at DFW, respectively. For both IAT and IAD, the Designating distribution is much more peaked and the peak skews slightly to the left as compared to the Not Designating distribution. This mirrors the descriptive statistics presented in Table III. The CAS-A distributions include less data but appear similar to the Designating data distributions with no obvious additional impact. Note that the minimum for all distribution curves is approximately the same, indicating that traffic designation is not changing

the current minimum spacing; it is just shifting the average in that direction.

FIGURE 8. IAT DISTRIBUTION AT DFW

FIGURE 9. IAD DISTRIBUTION AT DFW

One possible reason for the apparent difference in average and standard deviation results between the cases is that they represent different levels of demand at the airport. One might expect times of higher demand to naturally exhibit lower IAT and IAD with less standard deviation. To test this hypothesis, the average IAT and IAD were plotted vs. arrival demand (see Figures 10 and 11). Arrival demand was approximated by measuring the number of arrival aircraft that had landed during the past 15 minutes at the airport for each flight. The number of arrivals at the airport was used instead of the number of arrivals at the individual runway because DFW has arrival runways that interact with each other.

FIGURE 10. IAT vs. DEMAND AT DFW

FIGURE 11. IAD VS. DEMAND AT DFW

Figures 10 and 11 both show a steady decrease in both average IAT and IAD values as demand increases (to the right). However, the average IAT and IAD is less for the Designating case compared to the Not Designating case for every level of demand. This indicates that the reduction seen in the distributions is not solely the result of different demand loads but represents some difference in pilot behavior. As in Figures 8 and 9, the behavior for CAS-A flights is very similar to the full set of Designating flights. This suggests that the impact of CAS-A on IAT and IAD is similar and not additive.

To capture the impacts of both demand and traffic designation simultaneously, the team performed regression analyses with the following specification:

Dependent Variables:

- IAT
- IAD

Independent Variables:

- Arrivals in past 15 minutes at airport
- Behind a heavy (wake category) aircraft
- Downwind
- Designating Traffic (using traffic designation)
- CAS-A

Table IV presents the results of the regression analyses. When a coefficient did not have a statistically significant coefficient (i.e., the p-value >0.05) this was indicated with words “Not Sig.” in the table. The coefficient of Designating indicates a reduction in the IAT of 13 seconds and reduction in the IAD of 0.6 NM. The coefficient of CAS-A showed a small additional impact in IAT (2 seconds) and no significant impact in IAD. It is important to note that all CAS-A are also designating.

The impact of traffic designation on reducing IAT and IAD has been found to be similar across six American Airline hubs. Results in [24] present these results over a two-year period (January 2022 through December 2023) for CLT, DFW, LAX, MIA, PHL, and PHX.

If the 13-second reduction in IAT resulting from traffic designation (for CAVS/CAS-A) at DFW could be sustained for an hour, the runway throughput could be increased by 3 to 4 aircraft per hour for each arrival runway.

TABLE IV. IAT AND IAD REGRESSION RESULTS EXAMINING USE OF CAS-A AT DFW

Factors that impact IAT and IAD	IAT		IAD	
	Coefficient (sec)	P-value	Coefficient (NM)	P-value
Constant	134.9	$\ll 0.05$	5.5	$\ll 0.05$
Arrivals in past 15 min airport	-1.4	$\ll 0.05$	-0.1	$\ll 0.05$
Behind a Heavy	41.1	$\ll 0.05$	1.8	$\ll 0.05$
Designating	-12.9	$\ll 0.05$	-0.6	$\ll 0.05$
CAS-A (in addition to Designating)	-2.1	$\ll 0.05$	-0.03	0.23 Not sig.
Observations	104,413		104,413	
Adjusted R-square	16%		15%	

C. Flight time and distance in terminal area

While reducing IAT and IAD for CAVS/Traffic Designation and CAS-A arrivals is evident, what impact can be expected on the overall system in terms of reduced flight time or flight distance? Controllers at D10 have reported using CAS-A to reduce the flight distance during certain conditions. In one scenario, their increased confidence in the ability of CAS-A aircraft to accurately gauge distance has allowed them to reduce the downwind flight distance significantly by moving the aircraft into what would have previously been an unused or partially unused arrival slot. Figure 12 shows a few examples where CAS-A flights flew a considerably shorter downwind (measured within 25 NM of the airport) compared to other traffic during the same period. Figure 12 includes noticeable examples, although the statistical analysis suggests the average impact is lower. Controllers also indicated that they are more likely to use CAS-A to cut short a flight path in somewhat reduced weather conditions. When the CAS-A flight can reduce the flight path it also impacts the flights behind it allowing those flights to recover some of the distance previously committed to the unused arrival slot.

FIGURE 12. EXAMPLES OF CAS-A AIRCRAFT WITH REDUCED FLIGHT DISTANCES

To examine possible terminal area flight path and time changes, a regression analysis was conducted using 24 months of CAS-A operations at DFW. The data included aircraft trajectories from IOAA, CAS-A determination from CountOps, and airport weather from ASPM. Flights

during IMC were removed from the data because CAS-A is not allowed during those conditions. The regression used the following specification:

Dependent Variables:

- Flight Time 25 NM to runway threshold
- Flight Distance 25 NM to runway threshold.

Independent Variables:

- Downwind (0= No, 1=Yes)
- Go-around (0= No, 1=Yes)
- MMC2 (ceiling <6000 feet and visibility <=8 miles)
- MMC1 (ceiling <3500 feet and visibility <5 miles)
- CAS-A Ownship Downwind
- CAS-A Ownship Non-Downwind
- Arrivals at airport in past 15 minutes (number of aircraft in front)
- Heavy (wake category) arrivals at airport in past 15 minutes (number of heavy aircraft in front)
- CAS-A arrivals in past 15 minutes (number of CAS-A aircraft in front)
- CAS-A arrivals in past 15 minutes and MMC2 (number of CAS-A aircraft in front during MMC2)
- CAS-A arrivals in past 15 minutes and MMC1 (number of CAS-A aircraft in front during MMC1)

Table V presents the regression analysis results for both flight distance and flight time.

TABLE V. FLIGHT TIME AND DISTANCE REGRESSION RESULTS EXAMINING USE OF CAS-A AT DFW

Factors that impact Flight Distance and Time	Flight Distance Impact		Flight Time Impact	
	Coefficient (NM)	P-value	Coefficient (seconds)	P-value
Constant	23.5	<< 0.05	436	<< 0.05
Downwind	26.7	<< 0.05	352	<< 0.05
Go around	45.2	<< 0.05	811	<< 0.05
MMC2	2.2	<< 0.05	47	<< 0.05
MMC1	4.1	<< 0.05	94	<< 0.05
CAS-A Ownship Downwind	-0.9	<< 0.05	-24	<< 0.05
CAS-A Ownship Non-Downwind	0.2 Not Sig.	0.08 Not Sig.	1 Not Sig.	0.82 Not sig.
Arrivals in past 15 min airport	0.2	<< 0.05	4	<< 0.05
Heavy arrivals in past 15 min	0.1	<< 0.05	3	<< 0.05
CAS-A arrivals in past 15 min	-0.2	<< 0.05	-8	<< 0.05
CAS-A arrivals in past 15 min and MMC2	-0.5	0.02	-9	0.01
CAS-A arrivals and MMC1	-0.1 Not Sig.	0.12 Not Sig.	-2 Not Sig.	0.20 Not sig.
Observations	685,177		685,177	
Adjusted R-square	86%		77%	

The results of the regression analysis suggest the following:

- For each CAS-A downwind arrival there is a reduction in flight distance of 0.9 NM or flight time of 24 seconds
- For each airport arrival during MMC2 there is a reduction in flight distance of 0.7 NM or flight time

of 17 seconds for every CAS-A arrival ahead during the past 15 minutes

- For each arrival during other non-IMC weather conditions (i.e., VMC and MMC1) there is a reduction in flight distance of 0.2 NM or flight time of 8 seconds for every CAS-A arrival ahead during the past 15 minutes.

The regression analysis was repeated using all CAVS/Designating Traffic aircraft as opposed to CAS-A operations but was unable to identify any statistically significant results for CAVS aircraft. This result suggests that this mechanism for terminal area flight time/distance reduction may not be available if controllers have no knowledge of which aircraft are using traffic designation.

The regression results in Table V can be used to create a monetized benefit using the measured data related to the number of downwind CAS-A arrivals and the number of all arrivals that have CAS-A aircraft arriving in the previous 15 minutes. The results indicate a savings of 11,869 NM in flight distance or 7,188 minutes of flight time over the 24 months of the study. Assuming an airline cost of approximately \$60 per minute, the total result sums to \$431,275 over the period. Transforming the measured time benefit into fuel and emissions benefits for an A321 results in savings of approximately 659,000 pounds of fuel and 944 metric tons of Carbon Dioxide. Considering that there were only 2,959 CAS-A operations during the 24-month period (about 2.2% of the total AAL A321 arrivals), this benefit represents only a small part of the possible benefit from this mechanism. For example, if we assume all equipped AAL A321 arrivals into DFW (i.e. ~132,000) had received a CAS-A the total benefit would be closer to 321,000 minutes of flight time savings with a value of \$19 million as well as a savings of 29 million pounds of fuel and 42,000 metric tons of Carbon Dioxide.

VI. SUMMARY AND NEXT STEPS

This study presents an examination of IAT and IAD at DFW where American Airlines has been using CAVS/Traffic Designation and CAS-A operations and further analysis of flight time and distance in the terminal area for CAS-A operation arrivals into DFW. The key findings are:

1. When pilots designate traffic using the AGD, they tend, on average, to achieve more consistent and smaller interarrival distances at the runway threshold,
2. When pilots using an AGD are under control of TRACON controllers who can recognize the equipped traffic and use a procedure like CAS-A, there are flight time and distance savings in the terminal area.

As discussed in Section V.B, while the average IAT and IAD decrease when pilots designate traffic, the minimums do not significantly change; this implies that pilots are not trying to get below current minimum spacing, they are just reducing variation in current spacing. Put another way, the application is not increasing theoretical runway capacity; it is, however shifting the average IAT towards the minimum

resulting in an increase in average throughput allowing better use of the existing capacity.

The small (but statistically significant) reductions in flight time and distance in the terminal area related to CAS-A are encouraging but represent only a small part of the potential of this technology for air traffic management. If properly incorporated into display and metering automation, the ability to globally reduce the average and standard deviation of the IAT and IAD has the potential to significantly increase airport throughput and reduce NAS delay [17, 23, 24]. Realizing these benefits will require additional automation investment from the FAA so that controllers can easily identify CAS-A capable aircraft and additional avionics equipage by the airlines. This work was done for the FAA SBS office in support of the AIRS project. Future analysis could use the findings presented in this paper to inform simulations to better integrate and justify ADS-B In applications within FAA automation.

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ACRONYMS

ACSS	Aviation Communication & Surveillance Systems
ADS-B	Automatic Dependent Surveillance-Broadcast
AGD	ADS-B Guidance Display
AIRS	ADS-B In Retrofit Spacing
ANSP	Air Navigation Service Provider
ASAS	Airborne Separation Assurance System
ASDE-X	Airport Surface Detection Equipment Model X
ASPM	Aviation System Performance Metrics
ASQP	Airline Service Quality Performance
ATC	Air Traffic Control
CAS-A	CDT Assisted Separation on Approach
CAVS	CDTI Assisted Visual Separation
CDTI	Cockpit Display of Traffic Information
CF	Compact Flash
CFR	Code of Federal Regulations
CLT	Charlotte International Airport
D10	Dallas TRACON
DFW	Dallas-Fort Worth International Airport
FAA	Federal Aviation Administration
FIS-B	Flight Information Surveillance-Broadcast
IAD	Inter-arrival Distance
IAT	Inter-arrival Time
IFP	Instrument Flight Procedures
IMC	Instrument Meteorological Conditions
IOAA	IFP, Operations, and Airspace Analytics
LAX	Los Angeles International Airport
MCDU	Multi-function Control Display Unit
MIA	Miami International Airport
MMC	Marginal Meteorological Conditions
NAS	National Airspace System
NM	Nautical Mile
NOP	National Offload Program
OOOI	Out-Off-On-In
OTW	Out The Window
PHL	Philadelphia International Airport
PHX	Phoenix International Airport
SBS	Surveillance and Broadcast Services
STARS	Standard Terminal Automation Replacement System
TBO	Trajectory Based Operations
TCAS	Traffic Alert Collision and Avoidance System
TFMS	Traffic Flow Management System
TIS-B	Traffic Information Surveillance-Broadcast
TRACON	Terminal Radar Approach Control
VMC	Visual Meteorological Conditions

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